

How the Six/seven major plot archetypes discovered by Prof. Matthew L. Jockers can be explained

Author: Serhii Yaremko

Showshenk1@gmail.com

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Introduction

The article "A Novel Method for Detecting Plot" (Jockers, 2014) tells us how Matthew Jockers was impressed by the graphic plot shapes of Kurt Vonnegut - we could encounter them in the books "A Man Without a Country" (Vonnegut, 2007) and "Palm Sunday" (Vonnegut, 1981); the mentioned plot forms were beautifully edited by the designer Maya Eliam, among others (her poster is shown below (Fig. 1)).

Figure 1 (Image: Eliam)

In my opinion, Vonnegut's concepts are based mainly on these things: Life experience, professional experience, and intuition. We really do not know what method Kurt Vonnegut used to create his stories. Consequently, we do not find any thoughts of the author on the essential similarity between the story shapes "Boy Meets Girl" and "Cinderella" (this is made clear by the graph (Fig. 2) from the post of Staci Troilo (Troilo, 2021)).

Figure 2 (Image: Troillo)

On the other hand, Prof. Jockers proposes that the computer measure the emotional valence of all the sentences of a literary work one by one (to achieve this goal, he has developed the Syuzhet package for the R programming language). After analysing more than forty thousand English novels with the PC (this process reminds me of the discovery of the Mandelbrot set), we know the Six/seven major plot archetypes in literature; and I consider that these are the last word in the process of exploring the story shapes at this moment.

The aim of the work

Although Prof. Jockers has not expressed any thoughts on the concepts discovered (and he should not do such a thing), I want to find out if the Six/seven major plot archetypes have any significant meaning in relation to our existence.

Methods

I will use the method of analogies (its essence in finding bridges between what is familiar and what is very new to us) to answer the main question. As the main source of information about the story shapes, I would like to choose one of the posts of JD Lasica (JD Lasica, 2021).

Results

Story shape 1: Emergence

Figure 3 (Image: Jockers)

This plot means "Comedy", which generally tells about how, with the beginning of the Universe, order rather than chaos is created (we can learn a lot about it in the book "A Brief History of Time: From the Big Bang to Black Holes" (Hocking, 1998)).

Interestingly, we observe the latter concept all the time, as both the death of the Old and the birth process are common; it looks like a kind of live illustration (and now I can boldly claim that when we observe the action "Hero/heroine dies", the combination of "The enemy harms hero/heroine" and "The enemy dies", the actions, is seen). For better understanding this statement of mine, I would like to include an illustration from the professor's blog (Jockers, 2015) - I direct our attention to the upper right graph of Figure 4.

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Figure 4 (Image: Jockers)

Story shape 2: Man in the Hole

Figure 5 (Image: Jockers)

I believe that the present plot shape can be recognised as a revenge attempt of chaos (which we can additionally prove after observing the centre of Fig. 3), which was successfully overcome by order; and it can be seen through the great crisis events: a great annihilation that occurred shortly after the Big Bang (Hocking, 1998), the mass explosion of the First generation of stars (so-called Population III (Glover & Klessen (2023))), the extinction of the dinosaurs, and so on.

Story shape 3: The Quest

Figure 6 (Image: Jockers)

As for this plot archetype, I think we can clearly see the aforementioned attempt at chaos revenge by the second peak. Similarly, a supernova becomes brighter than the entire galaxy as the time of the explosion approaches.

Story shape 4: Rags to Riches

Figure 7 (Image: Jockers)

It can be clearly seen that the right part of Fig. 7 shows the process of order overcoming chaos attempt at revanchization.

Story shape 5: Voyage and Return

Figure 8 (Image: Jockers)

I think we can see that the observed Plot archetype 5 is the opposite of the Plot archetype 3 described earlier.

Story shape 6: Rise and Fall

Figure 9 (Image: Jockers)

Similarly, we see the antipode of Plot archetype 4 right now.

Story shape 7: Descent

Figure 10 (Image: Jockers)

And again there is an antipode, this time it refers to the first concept discussed (Emergence).

Discussion

I think the success measure of the present research can be determined up as seventy percent. Regarding to the object of the research - I mean the novel method for detecting plot proposed by Prof. Jockers (see the professor's blog for a detailed description) - the latter is very handy to work with, especially thanks to the professionalism of Matthew Jockers.

To explain the problem, I should attach a quote from "A Man Without a Country". Kurt Vonnegut, describing the shape of the plot "Man in the Hole", says: "It is not accidental that the line ends up higher than where it began. This is encouraging to readers." But Jockers' observed plot archetypes don't support this conclusion. Neither the confusion of the original researcher has taken place, nor is there any weakness in the method to be expected in this case. It is an essential characteristic of the corpus of literary works that it is generally not focused on details - this is the only cause. In this case, I would like to point out a mistake of mine: I believed that it was no coincidence that the trajectory I drew to show the change in status that disloyal revolutionary leaders have in society over time (Fig. 11, red line) is very

similar to the MOH Type 2 from Matthew Jocker's blog (Fig. 12), until I came across JD Lasica's post mentioned above.

Level (-1) - Imprisoned criminals; Level 0 - Law abiding citizens;
 Level 1 - An elected authority; Level 2 - Law (Order).

Main personae: Law (Order), First Servant, Second Servant, and Chaos.

Figure 11 (Image: Yaremko)

Figure 12 (Image: Jockers)

Conclusion

The six/seven major plot archetypes discovered by Prof. Jockers currently the most reliable among other similar concepts due to science methods used. And they reflect the struggle between order and chaos as shown. But it seems that the novel method of detecting plot is not yet fully recognised. You will easily find videos or scientific articles highlighting Campbell's monomyth, Propp's functions, but I repeat: the results obtained by Matthew Jockers are waiting for further exploration.

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